

PSYCHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF NATIONAL IDENTITY

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Abstract. *The article discusses the theoretical substantiation of the spheres of the polysystemic existence of a citizen as levels of functioning of national identity and their presentation in the form of a schematic model, as well as the presentation of a qualitative empirical model of the psychological factors of national identity that most influence the personality of a citizen.*

Keywords: *transformation, state security, determination, internalization, family.*

Introduction. The social transformations taking place in society can be characterized on a psychological level as a struggle for personal identity.

The formulation of scientific problems from this very perspective allows us to talk about the phenomenon of national personal identity as a basic prerequisite for national and state security and a guarantee of the harmony and proactivity of society.

We can define national identity as the individual experience of belonging to a particular state in the role of its citizen and to the community of citizens of a particular state, which allows him to act as a collective subject.

Thus, national identity acts as an identification not only with the community of fellow citizens, but also with the state as an organization that creates certain rules of the game in the form of a legal, moral and economic-financial field, which can contribute to comfortable living and the realization of the citizen's personality, or maybe, on the contrary, create obstacles to such implementation.

The crisis of national identity, on the one hand, and adherence to the basic scientific principles of psychology (systematicity, development, determinism, etc.), on the other, stipulate a comprehensive scientific consideration of not only the psychological phenomenon of national identity, but also the factors that can influence it. By a factor we will understand something that has a certain causal influence on a phenomenon, in this case - on national identity [1; 116 pages]. Psychological factors mark the influence of social phenomena on the human psyche, determining accordingly its cognitive, value, ideological, emotional and behavioral manifestations.

Main part. Speaking about the processes of formation and formation of national identity, it is necessary to determine the essential characteristics and the key difference between these processes.

In the process of formation, one can distinguish a spontaneous component (i.e. changes under the influence of uncontrollable, random factors, for example, informal teenage associations, advertising, fashion, music, etc., the nature and consequences of which are unpredictable), and a purposeful process of personality changes or its individual aspects and qualities due to specially organized influences. The concept of formation emphasizes the process of acquiring new signs and forms of the psyche in the process of human development. We can talk, for example, about the formation of character, thinking, etc., that is, this concept is advisable to apply when we are talking about the development of a particular aspect or quality of personality.

Thus, by formation we will understand a purposeful and artificial process of change leading to the transformation of a person's national identity. At the same time, formation is a natural process that influences the personality of a citizen throughout his life [2; 231 pages].

Taking into account the diversity of sources and driving forces of personality development, as well as the systemic nature of the determination of its mental phenomena and behavior, one should also attest to the effect of a number of factors on the process of formation of national identity at the macrosocial, microsocal and individual experiential levels.

At the macrosocial level, represented by society as a whole and large social groups, a citizen is influenced by macrosocial factors, assessing which, a person develops an attitude towards society, the state and its political and organizational system; a significant role at this level is played by the features of the political culture of society, as well as the state mass consciousness. Features of the political culture of a society are determined by the type of political system of the state. It includes knowledge and ideas about power, politics and the state formed over the course of many generations, defining values, instructions, myths and stereotypes, orientations, beliefs associated with the political system. At the level of the individual, political culture is the result of the internalization of elements of the political experience of society in the personal psychological structures of individual consciousness in accordance with the active construction by the individual of his own inner world.

A person's civil status is ensured only by his personal concern, realized in self-government at the community level. National identity in a situation of non-compliance by the authorities with the "social contract" and non-compliance with the democratic procedures of democracy can take on the features of a protest.

In this situation, pro-government discourse finds itself in opposition to national identity, which encourages its bearers to take responsibility for the community, rather than rely on power as the actual "subject" identity. It is not without reason that one of the fundamental features of civil society, which modern Western researchers point out, is "the legalization of civil disobedience, as opposed to the political sphere of the state [3; 157 pages].

The formation of national identity is intended to ensure the integration, unity and integrity of the individual's self-awareness as a citizen of a multicultural society on the basis of the appropriation of a system of universal moral ideas, the freedom of his self-expression, on the basis of taking into account the abundance of social meanings, values, attitudes and norms. In this regard, science is faced with the question of developing technologies and models for the formation of a new identity for young citizens, which is of strategic importance for the successful future of statehood.

At the microsocal level, the civil and political goals and values of society are transmitted mainly through small groups in which the individual is in everyday life and interacts with them. In the process of such interaction, the individual is involved in the sphere of citizenship and politics at an ordinary level, through primary social groups through direct communication and interaction. Such reference groups with which a citizen interacts become basic social institutions that lay the main semantic seeds in the structure of national identity. Such groups include family, groups of friends, acquaintances, educational and work groups, children's and youth organizations.

The psychological basis for the socialization of a person as a citizen is the family. It is the center of inheritance of knowledge, traditions, values, moral norms, and characteristics of relationships. It is in the family that an individual receives the very first knowledge about the

sphere of citizenship, gains experience of active participation or avoidance of participation in processes related to the role of a citizen.

An essential microsystem factor in the formation of a young person's national identity is also communication in primary social groups. Through direct interaction with members of such groups, a person learns ideas, norms and values, and forms styles of behavior in certain situations. However, the effectiveness of their influence depends on the level of significance of the individual, as well as on the level of development. The higher the level of development of primary social groups and the assessment of one's belonging to it, the greater the influence they have on the individual [4; 84 pages].

At the individual experiential level, factors influencing a person's national identity influence, in particular, the processes of formation of individual psychological constructs, on the basis of which needs and motives, various ideas and values regulating his consciousness and behavior in civil visions are gradually formed. At this level, an important role is played by both the socio-demographic characteristics of the citizen (age, gender, place of residence, etc.) and the psychological characteristics of the individual's life in the space that the state has built for him and the direct experience of interaction between the citizen and representatives of the state at different levels. , as well as direct experience of activity within the legal field and economic and financial space of a particular state.

As a result of such activity, the civic position of the individual is formed, which should be assessed in accordance with three parameters:

- favorable or unfavorable environment for one's own self-realization. And this, in turn, predetermines the attitude towards the state as "one's own" or "alien", "friendly" or "hostile" for the individual;

- orderliness of the social environment, its predictability and predictability, which is determined by the individual's need for security, protection from social expansion;

- a sense of justification for one's own existence, first of all, as a member of the community, as its integral component.

This feeling is caused by the need for a meaning of being, which a person can seek separately from others, or, on the contrary, by joining an organizational community and sharing (borrowing) its inherent system of meanings.

Thus, the individual evaluates not the power, but the organizational space formed around it, and in view of this assessment, various types of perception of the image of the state are formed [5; 49 pages].

The image of the state acts as a regulator of individual activity in the organizational environment of the state.

And it is the corresponding image of the state that influences the formation of national identity, acting either interactively (that is, unites civil society around state meanings) or destructively. The existing image of the state dictates the nature of the relationship between the state and its citizens. It can be maximally destructive (in the case of object-object relations), when a person perceives the state as a large mechanism (for example, an apparatus of violence), and himself as its cog, that is, he gives an objective interpretation to both himself and the state, and the most constructive, partnership (subject-subject relations), presupposing the recognition of the subjective primary source for each side of the relationship. That is, both in civil society and in government bodies.

Object-subject relations, like subject-object relations, presuppose an uneven distribution of subjectivity in the perception of the individual: in the first case, subjectivity is recognized by the state, the individual sees himself as a pawn in someone else's game; in the second, the role of the object of use is assigned to the state, and for oneself - the role of a source of activity.

Regarding the diagnosis of psychological factors of civic identity, it should be noted that this type of work is being carried out for the first time and, in our opinion, is a significant gap in the study of the phenomenon of civic identity, since it ignores one of the basic principles of psychology - the principle of development. Studying precisely from the position of the genesis of this phenomenon gives us the opportunity for more complete information and the ability to predict the main patterns of its further transformational dynamics.

Before directly starting to develop an approach to diagnosing civic identity factors, a number of problems that may arise during work and prevent reliable results were considered.

One of the most significant confounding variables, which, in our opinion, can have a significant impact on the results obtained, is the phenomenon of artifacts in psychological research as an experimental result arising from deviations in the conduct of the study.

The cause of artifacts may be the inadequacy of the experimental procedure used, when the researcher cannot foresee the factors that change the behavior of the individuals being studied. In connection with the need to solve these experimental problems and in order to level out the effects of various secondary variables, the following precautions have been introduced:

- conducting research anonymously;
- elimination of the possibility of penetration of subjects into the essence of the subject;
- with the help of instructions, providing respondents with those answers that come to mind first;
- construction of a convergent scheme for studying the factors of civic identity, aimed at identifying these groups of factors only empirically, without forming them theoretically. The theoretical analysis only outlines broader spheres of influence of psychological factors of national identity. However, the groups of factors themselves were identified thanks to the diagnosis of the semantic space of respondents' judgments based on their national identity and the organization of a pilot study to evaluate these judgments.

The procedure for developing the approach itself is based on the scaling model, but is not a strictly adhered implementation of it. The basis for this comparison are:

- formation of a list of judgments (features of obtaining material for subsequent content analysis);
- expert review.

To diagnose civic identity factors, a survey is first conducted, the results of which are analyzed using the content analysis method.

The obtained expert assessments will make it possible to select the main judgments on three scales, in accordance with the main areas of a person's life, such as: macrosocial, microsocial and individual experience.

Conclusion. The results obtained by the researchers during the empirical study of the psychological factors of the national identity of young people showed that the formation of this psychological phenomenon is most influenced by the citizen's readiness to migrate, the feeling and experience of justice, the opportunity to realize oneself as a citizen of one's state, the locus of control, as well as the citizen's experience in the legal, economic and financial field of the state.

Thus, the identified and analyzed factors included in the regression model act as factors of a person's national identity. All of them function within the framework of the designated levels of polysystemic existence of the citizen's personality as spheres of action of the specified factors influencing national identity, namely: macrosocial, microsocial and individually experienced.

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